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Assessment and adaptation to climate change and sea level rise impacts on Egypt's northern coasts

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Abstract. Climate change and sea level rise (SLR) represent many challenges for coastal areas such as coastal erosion and saltwater intrusion (SWI). This study aims to highlight the effect of climate change and SLR on Egypt's northern coasts and present appropriate adaptations. A number of techniques for adapting with climate change and SLR have been presented. Two numerical models have been used for simulation PLAXIS and 2D-FEST. The results showed that SLR will affect a number of cities on Egypt's northern coasts and the Nile Delta aquifer will be affected by SWI. A number of scenarios have been applied to adapt with climate change and SLR. Precast Diaphragm Wall (PDW) is used to protect Egypt's northern coasts from SLR. The results showed that PDW is applicable and cost efficient. The cost of building PDW along the north coasts is about 1.0% of the likely losses due to SLR in 2100. However, to control SWI into the Nile Delta aquifer a number of measures have been presented and discussed. The results revealed that using treated wastewater to increase the recharge to the Nile Delta aquifer combined with decreasing the abstraction from the aquifer could help in protecting the aquifer from probable SLR.

1. Introduction

Climate change is accelerating as a result of human activities and natural processes. Climate change could have negative consequences if it continues. Weather patterns could shift, resulting in flooding, drought, erosion, wetlands loss and seawater intrusion into fresh groundwater aquifers. Global warming is regarded main cause of climate change, with the potential to melt enough polar ice to raise the sea levels. Global mean sea level rise was projected (10-20 cm) over the last century (IPCC, 1996) [1]. The rate of future sea level rise (SLR) is expected to outpace that of the past. SLR is expected to be (20 - 88 cm) by 2100 (IPCC, 2001) [2]. Long-term effects of SLR on coastal areas include; increase the coastal erosion, submergence of shore cities, saltwater intrusion (SWI), loss of agricultural land and increasing the coastal water table [3].

The Mediterranean region is more vulnerable to climate change. These areas are suffering from water scarcity, and its availability is decreasing in several countries as a result of population growth, which has increased abstraction and contamination of groundwater. Climate change could have direct impact

on water resource, salinization of coastal aquifers, soil degradation, and agricultural production at the Mediterranean basin. Climate change impacts on coastal cities should be addressed with appropriate adaptation measures.

Several studies have been conducted to protect coastlines from SLR (Baric et al., 2008; Fenger et al., 2008; Taormina and Chau, 2015) [4,5,6]. In addition, some studies in Egypt carried out to protect the coasts from SLR (Fanos et al., 1995; El-Raey et al., 1999; Heikal et al., 2012) [7,8,9]. A number of researchers have also investigated SWI in the Nile Delta aquifer while taking into account the SLR (e.g. Abd-Elhamid et al., 2016, 2019, 2011, Javadi et al., 2012) [10,11,12,13]. A few studies have been conducted to protect Egypt's coasts from the anticipated SLR. The current study aims to assess the impact of climate change and SLR on Egypt's northern coasts and present appropriate adaptation measures to protect coastal areas from expected SLR. In the simulation of groundwater flow and SWI into coastal aquifers, the PLAXIS and 2D-FEST models are used. Various techniques are also applied to protect Egypt's northern coasts from climate change and SLR.

2. Methodology

This research includes two stages. The PLAXIS software is used in the first stage to test the efficacy of using Precast Diaphragm Walls (PDW) to protect coastal cities on Egypt's northern coasts from SLR. Controlling the coastal erosion and shoreline inundation could be accomplished through a variety of methods. Offshore breakwaters, perched beaches, groins, revetments, dikes, floodwalls, seawalls, bulkheads, and dams are examples of hard structures. Artificial beach nourishment, dune building, and marsh building are examples of soft structures. Miscellaneous include structure elevation and strengthening of the existing structure. PLXIS (2-D) is used in the analysis of using PDW to study seepage around diaphragm wall and carry out the necessary analysis for the diaphragm wall design; more information on PLAXIS software can be found in (Abd-Elhamid et al. (2016) [14].

2D-FEST model was used in the second stage to investigate SWI in the Nile Delta aquifer. Climate change impact and SLR on SWI was studied and various SWI control scenarios were used to mitigate SWI. The differential equations for transient fluid flow and solute transport in saturated/unsaturated soils are given in terms of two primary variables; pore-water pressure (u_w) and solute concentration (c). The detailed information on differential equations and numerical solution of coupled fluid flow and solute transport can be found in (Abd-Elhamid, 2010) [3]. Water flow and solute transport differential equations are written as [3]:

Water flow equation:

$$C_{ww} \frac{\partial u_w}{\partial t} + C_{wT} \frac{\partial T}{\partial t} + C_{wa} \frac{\partial u_a}{\partial t} = \nabla[K_{ww} \nabla u_w] + \nabla[K_{wT} \nabla T] + \nabla[K_{wa} \nabla u_a] + \rho_w \nabla(K_w \nabla z) \quad (1)$$

Solute transport equation:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial((\theta_w + H\theta_a)c)}{\partial t} = & - \left[\left(\frac{\partial}{\partial x} (v_{wx}c) + \frac{\partial}{\partial y} (v_{wy}c) \right) + \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial x} (v_{ax}c) + \frac{\partial}{\partial y} (v_{ay}c) \right) \right] \\ & + \left[\frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left(D_{wxx} \frac{\partial}{\partial x} (\theta_w c) + D_{wxy} \frac{\partial}{\partial y} (\theta_w c) \right) + \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \left(D_{wyy} \frac{\partial}{\partial y} (\theta_w c) + D_{wyx} \frac{\partial}{\partial x} (\theta_w c) \right) \right] \\ & + H \left[\frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left(D_{axx} \frac{\partial}{\partial x} (\theta_a c) + D_{axy} \frac{\partial}{\partial y} (\theta_a c) \right) + \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \left(D_{ayy} \frac{\partial}{\partial y} (\theta_a c) + D_{ayx} \frac{\partial}{\partial x} (\theta_a c) \right) \right] \\ & - \frac{\partial}{\partial t} (\rho_b K_d c) - (\lambda_w \theta_w + H \lambda_a \theta_a) (1 + \rho_b K_d / \theta_w) c = 0 \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

3. Climate change and SLR impacts on the Egypt's northern coasts

This section of the study discusses the impact of climate change and SLR on coastal cities as well as coastal aquifers (Nile Delta aquifer).

3.1 Impact of climate change and SLR on Egypt's coastal cities

SLR will result in the loss of many coastal areas and increases SWI into coastal aquifers. It will also raise the water table and reduce the agricultural productivity. Because a large portion of Egypt's Mediterranean coastline is below sea level, it will be affected by sea level rise. Egypt's important cities, such as Alexandria, Marina, Marsa Matrouh, Rosetta, and Port Said, are located in or near these areas (Figure 1a). Also, the Mediterranean Sea water intruded into 100 Km in the Nile Delta aquifer (Figure 1b).

Figure 1. The Nile Delta location map and vertical cross section.

A number of studies discussed SLR impacts on these areas of Egypt (e.g. El-Raey et al., 1995-1996-1999a,b; Frihy, 2003-2009) [15,8,16,17,18,19]. These studies predicted that if not suitable actions are taken, Egypt would face the following consequences: loss of beaches, tourism, agricultural and fishing land. Over the current century, up to 15% of the delta could be inundated that extend to 20 km inland. Also, SWI could lead to contamination of fresh water, soil salinity and loss of land productivity. Egypt is among the top countries predictable to be affected by a 1.0 m SLR (Dasgupta et al., 2007) [20]. Satellite maps of the Nile delta clarifying the impact of 0.5 and 1.0 m SLR is shown in Figure 2 (Simonett, 2002) [21]. Some studies were conducted to assess the impact of SLR on Egyptian coasts. The Nile delta is the areas of high vulnerability, as well as potential socioeconomic consequences, have been broadly defined. Alexandria, Beheira, Port Said, and Damietta are among the high-risk areas. El-Raey, (2010) [22] presented SLR impact on environmental and socioeconomic aspects of these areas. These cities are vulnerable to SLR and they will face significant challenges such as shoreline erosion, fisheries stress and SWI. Previous studies of these cities used various techniques and different scenarios of SLR 0.5 and 1.0 m to appraisal the probable losses (Elray, 1995-1999a,b,c) [15,8,16,17]. The losses at some of these cities in 2100 are expected as following: Alexandria (\$3.5 billion) and Rosetta (\$2.9 billion), [15,8,16,17].

Figure 2. The impact of sea level rise (0.5 and 1m) on the Nile Delta (Simonett, 2002) [21].

3.2 Impact of climate change and SLR on SWI into the Nile Delta aquifer

Seawater intrusion threatens several coastal aquifers in the world. The Nile Delta aquifer is one of the largest freshwater reservoirs in the world. Previous research found that SWI intruded to more than 100 Km in the Nile Delta aquifer. 2D-FEST model is applied to examine SWI into the Nile Delta aquifer. Figure 1a shows a vertical section through the mid of Nile Delta. The length of the section is 150 km, depths are 250 m on landside and 700 m on seaside. The equiconcentration line 1.0 moved in the aquifer to 112 km from the seashore (Figure 3a). Two scenarios are applied to investigate SLR impact on SWI in the Nile Delta aquifer (50 and 100 cm). Figures 3b and c show the results of the two scenarios. In scenario one when sea level is raised by 50 cm, equiconcentration line 1.0 advanced 4.5 km and reached 116.5 km (Figure 3b). In the second scenario, when sea level raised by 100 cm, equiconcentration line 1.0 advanced 8.25 km and reached 120.25 km (Figure 3c).

Figure 3. SWI in Nile Delta aquifer due to SLR.

The results indicated that SLR tremendously increased SWI in the Nile Delta aquifer especially if the second scenario is considered (SLR=100 cm) that increased SWI into 120.25 km into the aquifer which will lead to damage a large quantity of fresh water. The aquifer should be managed to protect the available freshwater using appropriate measures.

4. Adaptation to climate change and SLR effects on Egypt's northern coasts

This part of the study presents the adaptation techniques that could be applied to protect both coastal shore and coastal aquifers in the Egypt's northern coasts from climate change and SLR.

4.1 Coastal shore protection from SLR

Adaptation begins with identifying climate change impacts followed by evaluating the available options for dealing with the effects through changes in policies and/or building protection structures. Several adaptation management choices, including beach reinforcement, nourishment, construction of seawalls and breakwaters, change in land use, and development of comprehensive monitoring and decision support systems, can be used to protect shoreline from SLR [14]. Egyptian has started building coastal protection structures such as jetties, groins, seawalls, and breakwaters to face beach erosion. Fanos et al. (1995) [7] and El-Raey et al. (1999b) [16] provided examples of protection methods used on Egypt's northern coasts. Figure 4 shows sea barriers for combating piracy at Damietta for combating SLR (Russmerritt, 2008) [23].

Figure 4. Sea barriers at Damietta for combating SLR. (Russmerritt, 2008).

PDW is used in this study to protect coastal shores from SLR. PDW will provide stability, permanence, and water retention. As shown in Figure 5, PDW height is 10 m, 2.0 m above sea level and 8.0 m fixed in the soil. The efficiency of using PDW in stopping saltwater seepage is evaluated using PLAXIS model. A numerical study was carried out to investigate the effect of using PDW on head losses in leaking water produced by 1.0 m SLR. PDW thickness is 30 cm for a length of 10 m, with adequate reinforcement. The results show that PDW is effective at preventing seawater seepage beneath the ground's surface and has increased percolation length to compensate to 1.0 m water level difference produced by SLR. More information about the PDW design can be found in (Abd-Elhamid et al., 2016) [14].

Figure 5. PDW and designed cross section.

The cost of making 1.0 m of PDW is estimated to be \$1000. This cost include investigations, drilling, supports, walls, water stop, and finishing. This means each kilometre of PDW costs \$1.0 million. The expected losses for Alexandria in 2100 is \$3.5 billion (if no action is taken) [16]. According to this study, building PDW along Alexandria coasts \$35.0 million that represent only 1.0% of the likely losses. In addition, the cost of constructing PDW along North Coasts (1000 Km) length is \$1.0 billion. However, building a PDW with a length of 1000 km takes time, but it can be done on stages depend on priorities. The cost of constructing PDW with 1000 km length may be high, but it represents only 1% of the expected losses if nothing is done.

4.2 Nile Delta aquifer protection from SLR

2D-FEST model is applied to control the SWI into the aquifer using various scenarios such as decreasing abstraction, increasing recharge and combination of the two. To avoid the increase in SWI due to SLR, the pumping rate should be reduced (50%). When this is applied to the model, SWI has retarded by 4.5 km toward the sea (Figure 6a). Another scenario is used in which the aquifer's recharge has increased (50%). This resulted in a 5.0 km retardation in SWI (Figure 6b). However, combining the two scenarios resulted in a greater retardation of SWI to 8.5 km (Figure 6c). The results indicated that to adapt with the SLR 1.0 m that resulted in increasing SWI into 120.25 km, the abstraction should be reduced by 50% and recharge should be increased by 50%. This scenario could be able to mitigate the impact of climate change and SLR.

(a) Decreasing abstraction from the aquifer (50%)

(b) Increasing the recharge to the aquifer (50)

(c) Combination of decreasing abstraction and increasing the recharge to the aquifer

Figure 6. Mitigation of SWI in Nile Delta aquifer.

5. Conclusion

Climate change and SLR are expected to have significant effect on Egypt's coastal areas. According to previous research, sea levels will rise by (20 - 88 cm) at 2100. If nothing is done, this rise could have far-reaching consequences for Egypt's northern coasts in the long run. This paper examined impacts of climate change and SLR on coastal cities as well as the Nile Delta aquifer. Protection measures for Egypt's northern coasts have also been proposed. A detailed study of using PDW to protect Egypt's coasts from SLR is presented. The cost is evaluated against the economic losses that would result due to SLR if no act is taken. According to the results, the cost of constructing one kilometre of PDW is \$1.0 million. Alexandria city could be protected with a 35 kilometre coast length at a cost \$35.0 million. However, if nothing is done, the predictable losses at 2100 are around \$3.5 billion. Using PDW along Egypt's northern coast of length 1000 km will cost \$1.0 billion, which represent 1% of the economic losses caused by SLR. On the other hand, SLR of 50 cm increased SWI by 4.5 km and SLR of 100 cm increased SWI by 8.25 km. Different scenarios have been applied to protect the Nile Delta aquifer SWI increase due SLR. Three scenarios have been applied including; reducing abstraction from the aquifer (50%), decreasing recharge to the aquifer (50%) and combination of the two. Decreasing abstraction from the aquifer resulted in retarding SWI toward the sea by 4.5 km. Increasing the recharge to the aquifer resulted in retarding SWI 5.0 km. However, combination of the two scenarios could result in more retardation to SWI to (8.5 km), which could mitigate the likely impact of SLR.

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